

RESCUER
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Showing the
way to the future
of **Emergency**
Responders

RESCUER

In recent years climate crisis has destabilised our ecosystems causing natural disasters (droughts, floods, storms, and wildfires).

Accordingly, a significant proportion of the EU workforce is involved in emergency activities and disaster control and this is expected to grow in the upcoming years.

In such crisis situations, confusion can quickly escalate into panic, both among victims and First Responders (FRs), since one group's panic can easily infect the other. Fear and panic constitute the greatest dangers, especially in darkness and smoke situations, or extreme weather.

In panic's infectious nature, even a small improvement at individual level can have considerable benefits to overall social resilience.

RESCUER is focused on designing and developing a First-Responder-centered technology toolkit, through the "HERO" (enHanced nEw eRa first respOnder) concept.

How do we make our FRs superheroes? For instance, in search and rescue operations, RESCUER tools and systems will allow for faster positioning of FRs as well as faster localisation of victims and improved operational efficiency of FRs.

RESCUER delivers a toolkit offering:

Sense augmentation through enhanced sensorial input.

Precise and infrastructure-less self-positioning.

Cognitive support and multi-sense AR interfaces, improving FRs focus and capability to utilise information.

Robust ad-hoc intra-team communications for both verbal and data exchanges, all delivered over enhanced power and communication autonomy features.

RESCUER leverage technologies in an efficient way, turning FRs to the true equivalent of superheroes that prevent disaster and save lives. This, in turn, will further increase the public's trust towards FR agencies.

The expected reduction of risks to life and property will make a direct contribution towards safeguarding the fundamental rights and freedoms of EU citizens.

